

POSITIVE POSSIBILITIES OF COOPERATION BETWEEN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRACTICE IN LAW ENFORCEMENT ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *It is argued that the success of the activities of internal affairs bodies is based on scientifically based education, ensuring the formation and development of relevant competencies of employees of internal affairs bodies. It is argued that for law enforcement agencies, it is important to improve the cooperation of international law enforcement agencies that ensure international law and order, international and national security. It is proved that such a statement is especially relevant in our country due to the growing daily flow of tourists from different countries, with their different legal, national and political characteristics, customs and religions. It is argued that there is currently a clear trend of integration processes in the field of education of law enforcement agencies in Uzbekistan. It is argued that modern law enforcement officers need knowledge of the legal systems of various states, a broad worldview in the field of international law, linguistic competencies for business and professional communication in a foreign language.*

Keywords: *professional training, cooperation of law enforcement agencies, professional training of personnel.*

International cooperation of law enforcement agencies is an integral part of international cooperation in the field of crime prevention, detection and investigation of crimes, and treatment of offenders [1]. In Uzbek society, we are witnessing the process of transition from the humanistic-informational paradigm of education to the pragmatic-instrumental paradigm [2], that is, education is acquiring a competent-pragmatic form with a high professional orientation.

In order to form a clear idea of the forms and methods of international cooperation in the field of education and professional training of employees of internal affairs bodies, it is necessary to raise the quality of training, advanced training and retraining of employees of internal affairs bodies to a new, high level.

In the modern educational space for the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, this is achieved by developing fundamentally new, innovative educational concepts [1], which will undoubtedly have a positive impact on the quality of law enforcement in Uzbekistan.

For law enforcement agencies, it is important to improve the cooperation of international law enforcement agencies that ensure international law and order, international and national security. In our country, this is due to the growing flow of tourists from various countries with different legal, national and political characteristics, customs and religions that may differ fundamentally from ours.

The educational process of law enforcement officers should be continuous, taking into account the interests of the service regions.

Currently, there is a clear trend of integration processes in the field of education of law enforcement agencies in Uzbekistan. Modern law enforcement officers need knowledge of the legal systems of various states, a broad worldview in the field of international law, linguistic competencies for business and professional communication in a foreign language. The most important role in the training of qualified personnel for law enforcement agencies is assigned to innovative international scientific and didactic educational institutions [3].

International cooperation of law enforcement agencies is an integral part of international cooperation in the field of crime prevention, detection and investigation of crimes, and treatment of offenders. For law enforcement agencies of foreign countries, as well as ours, it is important to improve international cooperation that ensures international legal order, international and national security.

One of the negative aspects of the integration and globalization processes is freedom of movement associated with the opening of borders, which has greatly expanded the area of the "criminal-geographical space": unimpeded movement of goods, capital, free movement of people. In their accompanying actions, law enforcement officers, of course, are obliged to take these differences into account to a certain extent (especially language differences [4]) and in emergency situations, knowledge of the language will allow more lenient measures to be taken, and in the case of benevolent actions - more favorable. The success of the activities of internal affairs agencies is based on scientifically based education, ensuring the formation and development of relevant competencies in internal affairs officers.

There is another problem that requires a special, in a certain sense, innovative approach. In the context of the intensification of international tourism and international mobility of people, the need for literate, educated employees is growing proportionally to the population, technical progress, and the well-being of people. Focusing only on the older generation of literate (i.e. having completed higher education) law enforcement officers is insufficient (there are few of them, and there are many problems) - a large number of new young generation is needed.

Due to this, the most important role in the training of young qualified law enforcement personnel should be given to international cooperation with foreign educational institutions for the training, retraining and advanced training of law enforcement officers, which take into account the needs of the younger generation to a greater extent.

Training young qualified personnel is a very important problem for Uzbekistan, first of all, in the context of the intensification of international tourism and international mobility of people. Young people have always been in the center of attention of the state policy of Uzbekistan and will remain so in new Uzbekistan and in the future, since Uzbekistan is a truly youthful country both in terms of numbers and age. As the President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "the progress of any state, its dynamic development, the successes achieved, the well-being of its people depend on the level of attention to the education of the country's youth. In this sense, attracting young people to solving state-important problems is a priority area of state policy for Uzbekistan."

Currently, large-scale reforms are being implemented in the country in all areas, work is being carried out at an accelerated pace to overcome the pressing problems of society, and comprehensive conditions are being created for the harmonious development and education of youth.

In the context of progressive integration and globalization processes, crime has acquired qualitatively new forms, the number of crimes related to international relations has increased significantly, and the number of international criminal syndicates is growing.

In order to create an effective system for combating international crime, various forms and methods of interaction between law enforcement agencies are being developed and are constantly updated. The content, organizational forms and legal regulation of interaction between law enforcement agencies are coordinated at the international level.

The tasks of optimizing the activities of educational organizations in the new conditions are:

- problems of interaction between law enforcement agencies in the field of combating crime and educational activities,
- ensuring high-quality international cooperation between law enforcement agencies in the fight against crimes and offenses,
- organizing professional training, retraining and advanced training of law enforcement officers.

The implementation of these tasks will allow modern law enforcement officers to become familiar with the knowledge of the legal systems of various states, expand their horizons in the field of international law, and master foreign language competencies for business and professional communication. In addition to the knowledge and skills acquired in the process of academic training, they will be able to expand them through a practice-oriented system of advanced training.

The purpose of seminars, conferences, and trainings is to identify and provide the necessary expert knowledge on the ordered topics, as well as to ensure the smooth online conduct of a conference or seminar while coordinating logistical assistance.

Management in internal affairs agencies must comply with national standards of management quality, so law enforcement agencies work together with national educational institutions.

Such a process of international cooperation will contribute to the formation of a clear understanding of the forms and methods of international cooperation in the field of legal education and professional training of employees of internal affairs agencies and will have a positive effect on the quality of all law enforcement activities in the country.

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